

Spatial Statistics Applied to Raynaud's Phenomenon

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Abstract— In 1862, Maurice Raynaud described what is now known as the Raynaud's Phenomenon (RP), characterized by episodes of vasospasms of the extremities, associated with typical color changes in patients exposed to cold. There are two forms of the syndrome: the primary Raynaud tends to present lighter symptoms, while secondary Raynaud might include necrosis, ulceration and gangrene, making it worth while the pursuit of differentiating these forms in advance. The purpose of this work was to apply variogram models through geostatistical analysis in thermographic images in order to analyze the heat diffusion patterns to better comprehend this disease and aid at its diagnose. We observed that the most frequent distribution models are the Gaussian, Exponential and k-Bessel models, due to the properties of the correlations of spatial thermal distributions in thermographic images. The Bessel model is present in 44% of cases of RP1, 70% of cases of RP2 and in 38% of healthy cases. The Gaussian model is found in 40% of RP1, 12% of RP2 and 10% of the Healthy group. The exponential model was most frequently verified in healthy subjects with 32%, while in cases RP1 with 12% and RP2 with 8%. Other models appear in smaller percentages in all groups, with special attention to some models that adjusted only to the healthy individuals, such as the Circular and the Logarithmic models. These adjusted models provide great knowledge regarding the heat diffusion patterns present in individuals with Raynaud's Phenomenon, aiding in the differentiation when compared to healthy individuals. Moreover, although the models alone cannot yet distinguish the primary form from the secondary form of the syndrome, it points future studies to viable directions to attain it.

Keywords—Raynaud's phenomenon, geostatistics, biostatistics, thermography, biomedical engineering.

I. INTRODUCTION

Studies point out that Raynaud's Phenomenon (RP) can be primary or secondary, with different prognoses [1]. The primary, known as Raynaud's disease, is a functional vascular disorder that occurs in sporadic response to cold [1], [2], [3]. According to Wigley (2002), the primary form of the condition has a higher incidence, with about 80% of cases [4]. The secondary form, also known as Raynaud's syndrome, appears due to a primary response. It occurs, however, as a secondary symptom of a structural vascular disease and is often associated with scarring, ulceration or gangrene [1], [5], [6]. The Raynaud's Phenomenon is not easily diagnosed clinically. The change in coloration is difficult to observe even in the winter, since most patients wait in a waiting room acclimated long enough for any color change to disappear [7]. This is especially true in developing countries where diagnoses tend to be mainly clinical. Then, the RP disease is

usually clinically evaluated by means of questionnaires, and can be aided by exams such as periungual capillaroscopy, antinuclear factor screening and inflammatory tests. In addition, auxiliary technologies have been tested to aid in this diagnosis, including thermography [8], [9], [10]. The Thermography techniques, used in conjunction with clinical observations and other complementary tests, may be of great value for the definition of the medical diagnosis of RP. With today's technology, a single image can contain thousands of temperature points, recorded in a fraction of a second, and it has all the characteristics of being a non-invasive, painless and safe method [7], [11]. By thousands of temperature points it is meant a large number of variables, and there is the base motivation of this study, to analyze the feasibility of using thermal imaging as a tool to aid in the diagnosis of RP.

For this purpose, geostatistics was used to reorder the spatial mechanisms associated with the thermal irradiation images given by the thermographic figures. The technique used was the variogram describing the spatial behavior of the data under probabilistic models. The original hypothesis of this work is that these models can distinguish the thermal behavior from a healthy individual to a patient portraying Raynaud's disease.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Thermography Techniques

1) *Photo collection*: A total of 279 volunteers aged between 18 and 68 years of age, all of whom were residents of the city of Curitiba and with autonomy of decision. Volunteers with cardiopathies, atherosclerosis or with mycosis, fungi or skin lesions were excluded.

The volunteers were asked to avoid hot baths and showers, creams, talcum powder, vigorous exercise until two hours before the test, feeding three hours before the test, avoiding caffeine and nasal decongestants for the day of the test.

The data collection environment remained at a temperature of 23°C, with change range of 0.5%, controlled and monitored with a digital thermometer therm-hygrometer with SH 112 cable from J-Prolab.

The photo collection images were acquired using thermographic camera Fluke thermography, model Ti400, sensor size 320x240, calibration range from 20.0°C, up to 80.0°C, version SOC 2.49.0, Ti400-15010268.

The volunteer responded to an anamnesis having its central temperature measured through the G-TECH brand's

non-contact clinical thermometer. After undergoing a 15-minute acclimatization process, the hands were immersed for 60 seconds in a recipient with water at 10°C, with submersion until the carpal level. The water temperature was controlled by a J-ProLab brand digital thermometer. After the immersion, the hands were dried with disposable absorbent paper in a delicate manner, remaining free from contact with the body or any object until the end of the test. Then images were recorded immediately after the hands were removed from the water and new images were taken every 5 minutes until 20 minutes after immersion, i.e. $t = 0$, $t = 5$, $t = 10$, $t = 15$ and $t = 20$.

2) *Image processing*: After the images were acquired, they were analyzed using *SmartView* software 4.3.29 [12] that comes with the equipment.

B. Statistical Analysis

The primary objective of this step was to find the mathematical models that best fit the variograms of the thermal distribution of each of the groups, in order to find out if it was possible to make a distinction between the groups only by using the models. First, all the individuals in the sample belonging to the RP1 (13 individuals) and RP2 (11 individuals) groups, in addition to 10 individuals in the Healthy group, were selected to testing on time $t = 15$. Finally the regions analyzed were in these groups.

1) *Semivariogram analysis γ* : The semivariogram function, which represents the intrinsic hypothesis, is used in Geostatistics to express spatial variability in a predefined direction [13]. The semivariogram is constituted as being the differences of the experimental values located at regular intervals, represented in the semivariance graph. In stationary conditions, the expected mean value is constant or zero, which reduces the semivariogram to the quadratic mean of the experimental value differences [14]. Thus, for a set of experimental values $z(x)$ and $z(x_1 + h)$, separated by the distance oriented h , we define the experimental semivariogram by the expression:

$$\sigma = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N(h)} [z(x_i) - z(x_i + h)]^2}{2N(h)} \quad (1)$$

where,

$N(h)$ is the number of experimental pairs;

h is the interval that separates $z(x_i)$ and $z(x_i + h)$.

It is emphasized that this expression of the semivariogram is valid only for situations of stationarity or quasi-stationarity. This is because, if the expected average value undergoes gradual changes in space, in such a way as to characterize a drift tendency, other structural evaluation resources should be applied. This inherent aspect of the semivariogram can be better understood from the definition of semivariogram, according to Davis, 1986 [15]. In our tests, the most frequently found models were:

a) *Exponential*: The adjustment is made through the exponential curve. The plateau (c) is the asymptote of this curve and the variographic amplitude (a) corresponds to the tangent of the curve at the origin with the plateau [16]. Its function is:

$$\lambda(h; \theta) = c_0 + c_e \left(1 - e^{-\frac{h}{a_e}} \right), "h > 0 \quad (2)$$

where: $\Theta = (c_0, c_e, a_e)'$; $c_0 \geq 0$, $c_e \geq 0$, $a_e \geq 0$. It is valid in \mathfrak{R}^d , $d \geq 1$. In this model, c_0 is the nugget effect and c_e the partial threshold, so $c_0 + c_e$ is the threshold.

b) *Gaussian*: The function is parabolic near the origin, which indicates a rather smooth spatial process. This model presents extensive variographic amplitude and the similar level to the exponential model [16]. Its function is:

$$\lambda(h; \theta) = c_0 + c_g \left[1 - e^{-\left(\frac{h}{a_g}\right)^2} \right], "h > 0 \quad (3)$$

where: $\Theta = (c_0, c_g, a_g)'$; $c_0 \geq 0$, $c_g \geq 0$, $a_g \geq 0$. It is valid in \mathfrak{R}^d , $d \geq 1$. Similarly to the exponential model, c_0 is the nugget effect and c_g the partial threshold, so $c_0 + c_g$ is the threshold. The effective range is $\sqrt{3}a_g$.

c) *K-Bessel*: Also known as the Matern model, it is defined by the function:

$$\lambda(h; \theta) = c_0 + c_k \left[1 - \frac{1}{2^{\alpha-1} \Gamma(\alpha)} \left(\frac{h}{a_k} \right)^\alpha K_\alpha \frac{h}{a_k} \right] \quad (4)$$

For all $h > 0$, where: $\Theta = (c_0, c_k, a_k, \alpha)'$; $c_0 \geq 0$, $c_k \geq 0$, $a_k \geq 0$, $\alpha \geq 0$. The $K_\alpha(\cdot)$ parameter is the modified Bessel function of the second α order type, and $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is a gamma function. It is valid in \mathfrak{R}^d , $d \geq 1$. This family of models has been referred to as the K-Bessel model in geostatistics because of its dependence on $K_\alpha(\cdot)$. Here, c_0 measures the nugget effect and c_k is the partial threshold (being $c_0 + c_k$, the threshold). This was the model with the highest frequency of observations with 70% adjustments in the RP2 case.

2) *Semivariogram generation*: For the semivariograms generation, some steps were taken. First, matrices were extracted with the temperatures contained in the thermal images obtained. The arrays are 240 rows per 320 columns. From these matrices, 500 points of each thermal image were randomly drawn with the aid of a program developed in MATLAB software [17]. After proper treatment of these points via Excel, they were run in a program developed in the statistical software R [18].

III. RESULTS

A. Adjusted Models

In all groups, models that fit the sample data were found satisfactorily. As shown in Table 1, although there is not only one model for each group, it was observed that the Bessel model is present in 44% of cases of RP1, 70% of cases of RP2 and in 38% of healthy cases. The Gaussian model is found in 40% of RP1, 12% of RP2 and 10% of the Healthy group. The other models appear in smaller percentages in all groups. The Exponential model was most frequently verified in healthy

Fig. 2. (A) and (B) RP1 individual, (C) and (D) RP2 individual and (E) and (F) Healthy. Photos on the left (A), (C) and (E) are original thermographies, and right sided (B), (D) and (F) are krigged images.

Fig. 3. Variograms over time for (A) RP1, (B) RP2, and (C) Healthy individuals.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The models fitted to the data collected, presented in the variograms. They are adequate and represent this data well. The Kriging technique shows us this visually, since the

krigged images reproduce the temperature changes that can be seen in the original images. Regarding the original goal of diagnosing individuals who have Raynaud's syndrome, it is visually clear the distinction of the groups, both in the variograms (where healthy individuals present a negative concavity) and in the 3D images of the variograms along the time (where the healthy ones show great peaks at lower times). Statistically some work has still to be done in this effort. A feasible proposal would be to verify the thermal evolution using Bayesian models for longitudinal data separated by phalanges. In this way it becomes possible to update the new information to the initial function and adjust the information in the space-time, considering the possibility of discrete events that include probit models or logits.

REFERENCES

- [1] HIRSCHL, M. et al. Transition from primary raynauds phenomenon to secondary raynauds phenomenon identified by diagnosis of an associated disease: results of ten years of prospective surveillance. *Arthritis Rheum*, v. 54, n. 6, p. 1974-1981, 2006. ISSN 0004-3591 (Print) 0004-3591.
- [2] POPE, J. Raynauds phenomenon (primary). *BMJ Clin Evid*, v. 2013, p. 1119, 2013. ISSN 1462-3846.
- [3] SPENCER-GREEN, G. Outcomes in primary raynaud phenomenon: a meta-analysis of the frequency, rates, and predictors of transition secondary diseases. *Arch Intern Med*, v. 158, n. 6, p. 595-600, 1998. ISSN 0003-9926 (Print) 0003-9926.
- [4] WIGLEY, F. M. Raynauds phenomenon - clinical practice. *The New England Journal of Medicine*, 2002.
- [5] HERRICK, A. L. The pathogenesis, diagnosis and treatment of raynaud phenomenon. *Nature Reviews Rheumatology*, v. 8, p. 469, 2012. Disponivel em: <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrrheum.2012.96>.
- [6] VALDOVINOS, S. T.; LANDRY, G. J. Raynaud syndrome. *Tech Vasc Interv Radiol*, v. 17, n. 4, p. 241-246, 2014. ISSN 1557-9808.
- [7] LIM, M. J. et al. Digital thermography of the fingers and toes in raynaud phenomenon. *Journal of Korean Medical Science*, v. 29, n. 4, p. 502-506, 2014. ISSN 1011-8934. Disponivel em: [Go to ISI://WOS:000335377900006](http://www.kjvm.org).
- [8] RING, E. F.; AMMER, K. Infrared thermal imaging in medicine. *Physiol Meas*, v. 33, n. 3, p. R33-46, 2012. ISSN 0967-3334.
- [9] VASCONCELOS, J. H. et al. Analysis of Methods of Classification of Breast Thermographic Images to Determine their Viability in the Early Breast Cancer Detection. *IEEE Latin America Transactions*, v. 16, n. 6, JUN, 2018.
- [10] CORTE, Ana Carolina Ramos; HERNANDEZ, Arnaldo Jos. Termografia Médica Infravermelha aplicada Medicina do Esporte. *Revista Brasileira de Medicina do Esporte*. v. 22, m. 08, p. 315-319, 2016, ISSN 1517-8692.
- [11] MEIRA, L. F. et al. Book. Termografia na reia Biomédica. [S.l.: s.n.], 2014. 31-41 p.
- [12] FLUKE TERMOMOGRAPY. SmartView 4.3.29. version 4.3.29. [S.l.], 2006-2017.
- [13] STURARO, J. R. Apostila de Geoestatística Básica. 2015.
- [14] CLARK, I. Practical geostatistics. Elsevier Applied Science London, 1979. xii, 129 p. : p. ISBN 085334843.
- [15] DAVIS, J. Statistics and Data Analysis in Geology. John Wiley and Sons, 1986.
- [16] WALLER, L.; GOTWAY, C. Applied Spatial Statistics for Public Health Data. Wiley, 2004. Wiley Series in Probability and Statistics. ISBN 9780471662679. Disponivel em <https://books.google.com.br/books?id=OuQwgShUdGAC>.
- [17] MATHWORKS INC. MATLAB. version 9.4.0.8. [S.l.], 2018.
- [18] R Development Core Team. R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing. Vienna, Austria, 2008. ISBN 3-900051-07-0. Disponivel em: <http://www.R-project.org>.
- [19] SOYER, R.; SUNG, M. Bayesian dynamic probit models for the analysis of longitudinal data. *Computational Statistics and Data Analysis* 68 (2013) 388-398.